

IoT based Smart Parcel Monitoring Solution for Trico International LLC, Salalah

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Abstract:

Cargo industries are one of the major systems providing services to customers to transport their goods and parcels to different countries for clearance and delivery of goods to the customer. In order to monitor the parcel in the shop and moving items are not monitored using any smart technology. In this research study, the project team is planning to develop a system with the support IoT technology to track and monitor the goods and parcel automatically and this will connect to the cloud to store all data. Customers will receive messages on their mobile once their parcel is received by the company. The IoT (Internet of things provide possibilities to track the parcel and goods in the company. The project team is planning to use RFID technology, a GSM module is used with a microcontroller to track and locate the goods in the organization. Radio-frequency identification (RFID) uses electromagnetic fields to automatically track tags attached to goods in the company. The tags contain electronically stored information. These tags with information are placed in the parcel. The project will connect some sensors in the company to maintain the required humidity and temperature and lighting facility for keeping the goods in good condition in side store of the company. The company is finding to hard to monitor and tracking parcels and condition of goods in the store. The proposed system will provide a complete solution regarding parcel tracking, delivery and maintaining good condition of goods in the company.

Keywords: IoT, Sensors, Goods, Cargo, RFID and Camera